

INDICATORS OF GRADUALISM LIKE, WHICH IN THE STRUCTURE OF A SIMPLE SENTENCE

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Abstract

The study revealed the peculiarities of the functioning of gradualism indicators such as, which in the role of adverb, conjunction and particle, pronoun and particle as a result of the actualization of semes genetically embedded in the word or the contamination of acquired semes and, as a consequence of this, the formation of homonyms. The purpose of this work: to analyze the gradual semantics and gradual function of lexemes like, what', to give a systematic, comprehensive description of the semantic features and functional purpose of gradators like, what', to identify and describe the conditions for the implementation of gradual semantics.

Key words: functional-semantic category, gradualism, gradual semantics, gradator, graduaseme

A word is a symbolic unit. It organically merges two sides - form and meaning. The form of a word, which is a complex of morphemes, expresses a certain content - the lexical meaning of the word. It is the lexical meaning of a word that allows the word to perform the main nominative function and should be considered in detail when characterizing the word as a lexical unit.

Each word in the Russian language has its own characteristics, which are realized in the process of functioning of the word in oral or written speech. To study the lexical system of a language, it is necessary to identify paradigmatic, syntagmatic and denotative connections and oppositions between words. This path is productive for studying word classes. But it is also necessary to study the lexical system of a language through the study of individual lexemes, their functioning in the system of language and speech.

The system of grammatical structure of the modern Russian language is formed by linguistic phenomena that have a full set of differential features. These are key schemes (models) according to which typical linguistic facts are realized, clearly representing grammatical categories. Typical linguistic facts (“extreme cases” in the words of L.V. Shcherba) easily fit into the headings (“cells”) of various classifications and, as a rule, do not raise questions.

Researchers of the grammatical structure of the Russian language discover speech material that does not fit into the strict framework of even the most detailed classifications. In living language and speech, facts prevail that do not have a complete set of differential features of any one grammatical category. Such cases give rise to the existence of “difficult questions of grammar.”

A significant part of the answers to “difficult questions of grammar” are provided by observations of transitional phenomena characterized by syncretism of properties, the combination (synthesis) in one fact of language and speech of differential features of different grammatical categories.

The phenomena of transitivity permeate the entire system of language, but they are especially important in the classification of morphological categories and structural-semantic types of sentences. The zone of syncretism violates the clarity of the classification of parts of speech and types of sentences, however, transitional phenomena cannot be discarded when creating a classification, since their existence and the unlimited possibilities of their formation are one of the

most important sources of enriching the structural and semantic resources of the Russian language and speech. S. Bally notes: “Thanks to intercategory substitutions, thought is freed, and expression is enriched and receives different shades” [Bally, 1956, p. 143].

In modern linguistics, there is a tendency to describe specific linguistic facts in the lexical-semantic aspect, without their grammatical qualification, without determining their place in morphological and syntactic classifications, in the system of linguistic categories. Analysis of speech material outside the grammatical system does not provide a complete picture of the functioning of these facts, their interaction with others, and does not show their multidimensional nature.

The compatibility of words is determined by their lexical and grammatical properties. A change in syntactic functions often entails a change in the part-speech affiliation of words and groups of words. And this, in turn, makes it possible to change their lexical and grammatical properties and, in particular, the nature of their compatibility. A change in the nature of compatibility does not accompany all transposed words, but in some cases this sign turns out to be very significant.

Functional homonyms, following V.V. Babaitseva, we understand them as “etymologically related words that have the same sound, but belong to different parts of speech” [Babaitseva, 2000, p. 194]. An important objective of the dissertation research is to study the gradual semantics of functional homonyms. For this purpose, the following concepts are used in the dissertation: gradation, gradational relations, gradation, gradator, gradoseme, gradational (gradational) function, gradational vocabulary, introduced into linguistic practice by S.M. Kolesnikova (see works by Kolesnikova, 1998-2005). The linguistic concept of the theory of gradualism, which includes the listed concepts, is described in detail in the monographic studies of S.M. Kolesnikova.

Following S.M. Kolesnikova, by graduality we understand a functional-semantic category in which the meaning of the measure and degree of manifestation of a feature, process, phenomenon in relation to a neutral point (norm) is expressed by multi-level linguistic means: word-formation, lexical, morphological, syntactic and stylistic (see Kolesnikova, 1999).

The interpretation of gradualism as a functional-semantic category contains a connection with reality, with thinking, points to specific linguistic means, formal indicators of grammatical categories that constitute and form gradualism, and also suggests multi-level ways of expressing it. The concept of gradualism correlates with the concepts of “gradational relations”, “gradation”. These terms express interrelated but different phenomena belonging to different aspects of language.

The concept of gradational relations is associated with subject-object relations in the grammatical aspect. Gradational relations are established by the speaking subject. The impression created as a result of grading and highlighting the measure and degree of manifestation of the characteristic by the speaker is created through the design of degrees of comparison, objective assessment, methods of verbal action with the meaning of the measure, etc.

Graduation relations can be presented explicitly and implicitly and are the basis for creating opposition (opposition).

From the point of view of the relationship between members of the opposition, gradual oppositions are distinguished (stepwise), when members differ from each other in varying degrees of the same attribute.

Gradation (Lat. - gradual increase - step, degree) is understood ambiguously. In the term “gradation,” two elements of meaning are distinguished: 1) consistency, gradualness in the arrangement of the gradation scale, the division of gradation into stages, steps; 2) a stylistic figure, consisting of arranging a number of words in order of increasing (climax) and decreasing (anti-climax) of their semantic and emotional meaning.

Graduation is the correlation (ordering) of a qualitative feature in relation to a neutral feature (norm) on a gradation scale. Graduation is carried out using gradators “more”, “less”, “equal”.

The main working concepts when constructing a conceptual grading apparatus are:

1) establishing a zero level of measurement (norm) in a certain place in an open structure;

2) placement of values in relation to the zero level of measurement based on the “more”, “less” graders; “above”, “below”, etc.;

3) comparison of individual gradable meanings of words belonging to the same class;

4) sequential transition of one quantity to another;

5) the formation (as a result of interpolation [change, distortion]) of a continuous gradation scale between clearly expressed ascertaining meanings and implicit concepts associated with the movement of gradation.

The term gradator has a double nomenclature: (1) when used as a general grading concept through which the transition from one characteristic to another is carried out, where the gradator performs the function of a metaword. Gradators "more than", "less than" ("more than", "less than") are based on the principle of "wrapping". Thus, when comparing homogeneous features, objects, actions, conventionally accepted as A and B, the subject, speaking or thinking, “places” A in B. If A is within B, then the subject concludes that “A is less than B” (“B is greater than A”). In the event that A is outside B, then the subject states that “A is greater than B” (or “B is less than A”); (2) synonymous use of the concepts “gradoseme”, “gradation words”, that is, a gradator is a special means that

increases or decreases the degree of manifestation of a characteristic (affixes, lexical means, etc.).

The gradoseme serves as a unit of measurement of graduality. A gradation scale is understood as any (one) step, one step up (in the increasing direction) or down (in the decreasing direction) on the gradation scale. “Gradoseme” can be different linguistic manifestations: affixes, an additional sound, a letter, the word itself, etc.

Thus, “graduator” (in the 2nd meaning) is a synonym for a step on the gradation scale, and “gradator” is a linguistic manifestation correlated with a neutral point (norm) on the gradation scale, reflecting the actions of gradators, this is the result of gradation.

In the Russian language, the function of special means of expressing the category of gradualism is performed by gradual words (auxiliary gradational vocabulary), which are used by the speaking subject to convey the measure, degree of manifestation of a feature, process, action.

The term gradational function to varying degrees reflects the content of the speaker’s measuring attitude to the utterance. The gradual function realizes the communicative goal of expressing the highest / (lowest) degree of a characteristic of various objects of reality [Kolesnikova, 1999]. This function, like other functions of language, has two components: function-potency and function-realization (see Beloglazova, 2003).

The difference between the two considered aspects of the gradual function of linguistic units is clearly revealed in the dynamics of speech, in the process of formation of a gradual utterance. A potential grand function may be possessed by those means of language that in their meaning have a seme of measure and degree of manifestation of the attribute; a gradual function-realization - those means that actively function with the specified seme in speech. In the Russian language, there are means (except word-forming ones) that potentially do not have a gradual

function, that is, in their meaning they do not have a sense of measure, the degree of manifestation of a feature, but in speech, when updating the measuring perception of an object, these means can perform a gradual function.

Depending on the purpose of the utterance, the gradual function in Russian can be either primary or secondary. This phenomenon is observed in three-dimensional units of language: lexemes, sentences, etc. In word-forming means that belong to two-dimensional units of language and have a gradoseme, the gradual function is always primary.

The concept of the human factor in gradual semantics allows us to highlight the gradual function “as the purpose of the utterance - an indication of the degree of magnitude of the attribute of the gradable object in communication” [Kolesnikova, 1999, P.383]. The subjectivity of the gradual concept and the objectivity of the means of its expression represent a complex interweaving of the semantic and grammatical in linguistic units, acting as the mechanism of action of the language system to express the gradual function. The system of gradual means of expression reflects the picture of the speaker's measuring attitude. The choice of means of expressing measurement relations depends on the point of view of the grading subject [see. Kolesnikova, 1999].

Gradual vocabulary is divided into two groups - main and auxiliary [Kolesnikova, 1999]. The main gradational vocabulary is represented by words where the graduated meaning is contained in the lexeme itself (huge - tiny; wise - stupid), or the function of a gradator is performed by affixes (overtone, super-fast, sweet, open a little; little room, cold, rude). Auxiliary gradational vocabulary consists of syntactic quantifiers that perform the function of a “graduator” (that is, they take part in the expression of graded meaning in combination with the main gradational vocabulary: adverbs of measure and degree, particles, modal words). They should be considered as semantic units that have an independent status and are characterized by the following features: the number of auxiliary gradational

words is limited, they do not change, their meaning enhances the meaning of inflectional units. For example: how beautiful, how gentle; how interesting, how sweet, etc.

The gradual sememe “(highest)” or “(lowest) degree of a characteristic”, “ultimate degree of a characteristic” presupposes the obligatory presence in speech or thought of a subject and an object of a measuring relationship. The gradual sememe of the magnitude of a feature is the initial unit of gradual meaning and represents linguistic semantics that explains the mental content of gradualism. Gradoseme (gradual seme) is an analogue of word forms, the content plan of which includes lexical, word-formative and grammatical aspects of meaning.

The gradual (gradational) function and semantics are characteristic of significant and auxiliary words, depending on the conditions of their use and the logical-psychological essence of their meaning.

Adverbs of measure and degree reflect the syntagmatic aspect of gradualism. The main classification features of the adverb of measure and degree as are the degree seme “degree of magnitude of the attribute” and the function of indicating the degree of its magnitude, which is revealed in the syntactic structure. See: [Olya]: I really want to try this melon! (L. Karelin. Zmeelov) //fear as = “extremely”, “very”.

Relating to subjective-objective categories, pronouns express “the different attitudes of the speaker and the thinker to what he speaks and thinks about.”

The specific gradual purpose of the pronoun which to express the speaker’s measuring attitude to the communicated lies in its ability to replace an element (deicticity), in the property of non-nominativeness, as well as in the substitutive role and obligatory nature of the speech situation. The situational nature of pronouns makes it possible to actualize those conceptual meanings that are the

communicative task of the speaker. See: And what scars! Only on your hands or somewhere else? (L. Karelin. Zmeelov).

The pronoun which acquires a gradual meaning due to the function of the predicate, the method of derivation and the context. The use of pronominal words in a gradual meaning ensures the interaction of vocabulary and syntax in the functional-semantic field of gradualism.

For words that traditionally belong to the class of particles, a generally accepted semantic invariant (general partial meaning) has not yet been found. Common to all particles is the expression of the relationship of the message to the described reality, that is, the correlation of what is being communicated - from a certain point of view - with reality. V.V. Vinogradov notes the properties of particles - their “hybrid-semi-grammatical, semi-lexical type” [Vinogradov, 1972, P.521] and the intermediate position between adverbs and modal words, on the one hand, and conjunctions, on the other hand.

The ability to simultaneously establish contact with the interlocutor, connect a given statement with the previous one, express specific feelings and their complex (surprise, joy, grief), increasing the impact on the interlocutor, determines the complex dynamics of the functioning of particles. This dynamics can be seen only in a specific product of speech activity - an utterance that reflects the relationship between the speaker and the listener; context and speech situation. It is in the utterance through the means of language that the speaker’s attitude to extra-linguistic activity is expressed [Lekant, 1986, pp. 104-105].

One of the peripheral means of expressing gradualism are particles that contribute to the design of a wide variety of subjective modal characteristics and evaluations of the message. Entering into gradation relationships in the structure of the microfield, particles both perform the function of gradators. They introduce additional shades into the meanings of other words and give a special gradational coloring (increasing or decreasing the degree of a characteristic). Particles give a

peculiar shade to the sentence in which they are found. Only in a sentence do they have their own meaning, their meaning. Particles like, which participate in the expression of the gradual function in a statement.

Statements with particles like, which are located at the ends of the gradation scale, which correspond to the meanings of not the lowest / not the highest degree. The meaning of particles is correlated with the context and is used by the speaker to express the intensification of one or another degree of the attribute. The semantic functions introduced by the particles are “corrected” by the indicative nature of graded utterances, which in communication tend to interact with surrounding utterances.

Performing the function of gradators, particles like, which dynamize the meanings of other words or statements as a whole relative to the norm in the direction of strengthening or decreasing the attribute. See: [Nazansky to Romashov]: No, if I get hit by a train, and my stomach rips, and my insides mix with sand and wrap around the wheels, and if at that last moment they ask me: “Well, now life beautiful? - I will say with grateful delight: “Oh, how beautiful she is!” How much joy vision alone gives us! And there is also music, the smell of flowers, sweet female love! And there is the most immeasurable pleasure - the golden sun of life, human thought! (A.I. Kuprin. Duel);

With what young and boundless faith the soul is again full! How in this silence With everything, with everything that life has given, completely satisfied, it does not require anything else.

A.A. Fet. “I will go towards them along a familiar path.”).

Once in the graduality field, the value of the graduation object changes relative to the zero degree of measurement (norm). The catalysts (intensifiers) of this process are gradator particles. By grading the utterance and functioning as means of intensification, particles like, which attach special meaning to a word (expression), introduce a gradual-evaluative characteristic of the subject of mental

and speech activity. The manifestation of this meaning is directly influenced by the following factors: context, intonation, word order in a sentence, and the communicative intention of the speaker.

Particles are not only peripheral exponents of modality, evaluation and gradualism, but also unique indicators of changes occurring at the lexical, grammatical, syntactic and stylistic levels at the text level.

In the gradual fragment of the linguistic picture of the world, indicators of gradualism express “hidden”, subjective, and “explicit”, objective, meanings of graded and gradual evaluative statements to enhance the qualitative attribute, thereby participating in the implementation of the speaker’s communicative intentions. Indicators of gradualism such as, which in the process of communication bring together the inner worlds of the speaker and the listener and reveal transitional phenomena in the system of parts of speech, reflecting the “idea of relationships.” The semantic devices of these phenomena are formed by the context, intonation, and situation of speech. The information we read between the lines depends on the context and the stereotype of thinking.

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